

CLASSIFICATIONS OF CARDINAL NUMBERS AND ORDINAL NUMBERS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: In this article, the comparative analysis of the different aspects of cardinal number and ordinal number in English and Uzbek languages and their similarities are described. At the same time, the classifications of cardinal number and ordinal number are explained on the basis of linguistics.

Keywords: Morphology, numerical lexemes, grammar, cardinal number, ordinal number.

Introduction: In the department of morphology, word groups, grammatical meanings and grammatical categories of words are studied. One of the independent word groups, **number** in linguistics - the number of the subject - indicates the number, quantity and order of placement. They are usually an answer to one of the questions like "**how many, how many, how many**". The numbers are connected to the noun and indicate the quantity and order of the object represented by the noun. For example, *two friends, three friends, fifth grade* and so on.

Cardinal numbers are called quantity numbers in some literature. If we consider this situation in terms of number lexemes, number lexemes are those lexemes that represent the quantitative sign of the subject. Numerals are divided into two according to their meaning and grammatical features:

1. **Cardinal numbers;**
2. **Ordinal numbers.**

Cardinal numerals - numbers indicating the quantity and total amount of the object are recorded in the following form: *one, two, three, ten, and hundred*. A cardinal number is used in mathematics as the name of a certain quantity. For example: the introduction of an adjective before *hundred-, thousand-* indicates that these lexemes are actually noun lexemes. Even the number *ten* has such a feature and this situation is created as follows: the numbers *eighty, ninety* are originally composed of the lexeme *ten* as an adjective. For example: *eight + ten = eighty, seven + ten = seventy*. In Uzbek language, the types of cardinal number formation and their properties, when used in a sentence, as in other languages, are based on their own rules and create a new form of the word without losing its value.

For example: Mirbobo Do'stning maoshi durust bo'lsa ham, ikki o'g'il bir qizni bekdodalar kabi kiyintirishga va boshqa harajatlar uchun yetmaydi ("Avlodlar dovoni" novel). In the example given in Uzbek, the cardinal number did not undergo any phonetic change. The numbers continued to be written as they were, that is, *ikki o'g'il, bir qiz*. These words are used in the sentence as a cardinal number.

If we compare this situation with the English language, the similarities and differences between them will be evident. The use of cardinal numbers in English is similar to the Uzbek language. In English, let's look at the position of the cardinal numbers in the sentence by analyzing them. For example: Although Mirbobo Dost's salary is decent, he does not have enough money to dress his two sons and

a daughter like nobles and for other expenses (“Avlodlar dovoni” novel). In this case, as in Uzbek, the cardinal numbers come together with the noun and indicate the total amount in the sentence. As we can see in the above sentence, **two** and **a** cardinal number came before the noun and did not undergo any phonetic change. “**A**” the article in the sentence corresponds to *one*. At the same time, they are called **Cardinal Numerals** in English. Cardinal numbers indicate the amount of person or things and are the answer to the question “**how many, how many**”: *one, two, three*. Like Uzbek, the English language has a rule and its own way of making cardinal numbers. The suffix **-teen** is added to the numbers 13 to 19 to form cardinal numbers: four -**fourteen**, six - **sixteen**. Only the numbers **three** and **five** do not obey the rule and change to the given form: **three** - **thirteen**, **five** - **fifteen**. Numbers denoting ten are formed by adding the suffix **-ty**: six - **sixty**, seven - **seventy**. In this case, the form of numbers **two, three, four, five** changes: two - **twenty**, three - **thirty**, four - **forty**, five - **fifty**. Also, the indefinite article **a** or **one** is placed before the numbers *hundred, thousand*: *a (one) hundred, a (one) thousand*.

Another type of meaning of the number word group that should be covered in the article is **the ordinal number**. A type of number formed from a cardinal number with the affixes **-nchi, -inchi** is called an ordinal number in Uzbek language. For example: Qani, tanishib qo'yaylik: mening otim Hayitvoy, yettinchi sinfda o'qiyman (“Sehrli qalpoqcha” novel). In the given example, we can see that the word *yettinchi* is used as an ordinal number. By adding the affix **-dan** to the ordinal number, the words *birinchidan, ikkinchidan* are formed and act as an introductory part. Ordinal number also acts as an adjective. For example: Toshkentdan atay sotib olib kelgan qirqinchi fanorlar qayyoqqa ketibdi? (“Shum bola” story).

If we compare this situation with the English language, we can see the difference between them. In English, they are called **Ordinal Numerals**. Ordinal numbers indicate the order of objects and are the answer to the question “**which, which, how many, how much?**”. In English, the suffix **-th** corresponding to the affixes **-nchi, -inchi** in the Uzbek language of ordinal numbers. For example: In English, 5th means 5inchi in Uzbek language. Only 1-, 2-, 3- order numbers are written as follows: 1st (first - birinchi), 2nd (second - ikkinchi), 3rd (third - uchinchi). *The first, second, and third* numbers that stand out among the ordinal numbers in English correspond to *birinchi, ikkinchi, uchinchi* ordinal numbers in the Uzbek language and are sharply different. Because in the Uzbek language, all ordinal numbers are formed by adding affixes **-nchi, -inchi**. For example: Your second composition is better than the first (English grammar). In English grammar, ordinal numbers are formed by adding **-th** suffix to all numbers except the first 3 numbers (first, second, third): Oh, let's get acquainted: my name is Hayitvoy, I am seventh grade (“Sehrli qalpoqcha” novel). In the above sentence, the word “*seventh*” means “*yettinchi*” in Uzbek language.

Conclusion: *Distinct languages have different grammars and formal principles. Therefore, there are many different aspects of them, and many scientific works can be carried out in this regard. In this thesis, the similar and dissimilar internal structure of the languages was clarified by comparing the classifications of cardinal number and ordinal number in English and Uzbek languages.*

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